

Factsheet template for Reinforced Concrete Components

Obsolete Structure Audit

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The *obsolete structure audit* is carried out prior to the deconstruction of a building. It consists in inventorying the obsolete structure's components and evaluating their properties. The collected information facilitates the integration of reclaimed components in the design of a receiving structure.

The factsheet summarizes all relevant information collected during the audit. It is normally an appendix of the report. This document proposes a template for the component factsheets to organize the data in a coherent and effective way.

For more information

Devènes J, Bastien-Masse M, Fivet C. Reusability assessment of reinforced concrete components prior to deconstruction from obsolete buildings. Submitted to Journal of building engineering; 2023.

Type : <input type="text" value="Type number"/>	Category : <input type="text" value="Category name"/>
<input type="text" value="Name"/>	

Location

Photos

Color and finishing

Connections

Type : <input type="text" value="Type number"/>	Category : <input type="text" value="Category name"/>
<input type="text" value="Name"/>	

Dimensions

1:

Cross-section

1:

Type : <input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="Type number"/>	Category : <input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="Category name"/>
Name <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	

Description	Condition and durability						
Construction year <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Damage class <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Material <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Actual location <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Initial function <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Carbonation depth [mm] <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Accessibility <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Toxic substance <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Anchor points <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>							
Exposition <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Mechanical characteristics						
Color <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Concrete density (ρ_c) <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Finishing <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck}) <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Overlays	Concrete young modulus (E_{cm}) <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;">Type</th> <th style="width: 30%;">Fixation</th> <th style="width: 40%;">Thickness</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/></td> <td><input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/></td> <td><input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type	Fixation	Thickness	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sk}) <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>
Type	Fixation	Thickness					
<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>					
Connection type <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>	Reinforcement young modulus (E_s) <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>						
Deconstruction tool <input style="width: 95%;" type="text"/>							

Component	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts					
	Subtype	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	Conventional demolition	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/u]	Conventional demolition

Additional information

Additional note	<input style="width: 70%;" type="text"/>
Attention point	<input style="width: 70%;" type="text"/>